

TEACHING DIFFERENT AGES

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Annotation: This article is dealt with the methods of teaching different age groups, especially teaching English to non-native students effectively by new ice-breakers, games and structures of the lesson.

Key words and expressions: teacher, different ages, methods, teaching, theme, English, students.

Teaching different age groups is more difficult rather than the same one, so teachers should pay more attention for every part of the lesson. Teachers should know the interest of his or her pupils very well, after that teacher can give something to students. Firstly, we divide the learners in some groups according to their age.

First group is elementary students who are 3-8, especially study in kindergarten or at school. One of the famous teacher Peter Kruger thinks that that age group learners are full of the fun. But it is effective to teach young students even it requires iron patient. Because of it, there are large amount of things which they are interested in, for example: toys, pictures, cartoons and teacher can teach them by using these things. But teaching this age requires forgiving more, since when children make a mistake, it does not matter is it huge or small mistake, they even do not pay attention for it [1]. Moreover, it is effective to teach children within no more than 20 minutes with 5 minutes breaks. On account of it, children get bored if we teach them more than 20 minutes and without break.

Second age group is junior high students who are in the process of discovering themselves and trying to be independence [1]. This age is more difficult rather than others, since in this period children want to be independent and they do not listen the word what teachers or parents say. But they are full with energy and

they do not know how and where spend the energy. In that case teacher must show the true way that will bring benefits in the future. In addition, as a teacher we should take the control of the pupil's knowledge in order to lead them to success. One of the American teacher says that there are some ways to keep them engaged in lesson:

1. Do not lecture them for more than ten minutes.
2. Do not read things aloud to them. They are perfectly literate.
3. Let them do as much independent work as possible.
4. Try to do an artsy or group project every week [2].

Furthermore, I think that we also know how to adopt materials during the lesson for different age groups. I mean that when we use the materials in order to teach our students, we ought to use correct one for their age. For instance, I teach the students who are under the 14 and, also teach who are over 14 about the life of the ocean or sea. Firstly, I think about what these age group are interested in more. After that when I prepare the materials for youngest age group, first I make ice-breaking activity in order to improve the interests of pupils to the lesson. For example, I may prepare a game which related to the topic. After, I explain the topic with the cartoon photos of the sea animals. After explaining the topic, I show them a short cartoon which has sea animals.

When it comes to the next age group, I make a warm-up activity which depend on the theme. For this group I give an activity related to their vocabulary. Then I explain the topic with background information and give reading or listening task about the sea life. In this stage the tasks should be harder than young one. If I allowed the pupils who are under 14 to watch a cartoon for fun or show the sea animals, I ask my students who are over 14 to watch the cartoon and analyze situation in it, learning new phrases and words.

Relaying on your theory, these cute children can either be the best young generation you will have the relax of teaching or a horrific group of mad kids that reduce grown men to tears. Educating young children truly is not for the fast shirker as it will take time to get into the sway of it. There are good chances that at some

aspects you will have to deal with crying, toilet problems, complain and student who has the attention length of a gold fish. Some useful types are:

Be clear and direct in how you speak. Use simple 1 or 2 word commands and be prepared to apply a firmer tone to your voice when need be.

Be animated and lively. Not everyone will be comfortable with jumping around, singing and dancing for an hour but it will certainly make you more likable if you are able to act silly in class.

Use TPR activities whenever possible: Kindergartens depend on response very well to TPR (Total Physical Response) based on activities by which they create the language by physical activities. If you are teaching wild animals, have the learners doing the activities and noises, when educating them senses; have them acting the facial expression etc.

Short-term, serious games and exercises: one of the bulk way to keep your pupils' attention and save time cooperating with tired kids is to continue things moving all the time. When planning your lessons, start off by introducing your grammar point or vocabulary then run through a series of 10 minute games and usually have back up plans. When you see learners dropping focus, move onto subsequent activity [3].

Change the environment: combine up your lecture room setting regularly to steer them away from boredom. Get them on their feet, swap the seating layout and take a sit them in a circle on the floor.

Do not be afraid to use your educating assistant: youthful newcomers will hostilities more than anyone to grasp your meaning in English.

Gimmicks: some small change or new object that you bring into class will feel like a completely new adventure to your young students. Surprise them with the aid of bringing in a reachable gimmick to use in your matters to do, for example, a dice, a puppet or some pictures.

Motivate the by giving prizes: candies clearly provide young children with an motivation to study but without this kind of opulence you can easily keep them

willing by giving them another award [3]. A high-five or pat on the back after a successful activity and at the end of class will make them feel like they have achieved something, as will the opportunity to do some drawing or coloring activities during the lesson.

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